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CONTENTS

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF FREE ECONOMIC ZONES.....	51
Mamadiev Elyor	
IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY GUEST HOUSES	55
Boynazarov Ulugbek Egamberdievich	
IMPROVING METHODS OF ORGANIZING AND DEVELOPING DOMESTIC TOURISM MARKETS IN UZBEKISTAN	61
Daminov Mirvokhid Isroilovich	
THE IMPACT AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR.....	67
Dilsora Ibodovna Ibodova	
IMPACT OF STUDENTS AGED OVER 40 ON ECONOMIC ACTIVITY AND BUDGETING BASED ON THE COMPETENCY ECOSYSTEM.....	74
Nigora Ikrom qizi Primova	
ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ: ЭКОНОМЕТРИЧЕСКОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ И СЦЕНАРНОЕ ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЕ НА 2026–2030 ГОДЫ	80
Юсупов Шерзодбек Бахтиёр угли	
IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE PROCUREMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN COMMERCIAL ENTERPRISES.....	87
Ergashev Jahongir Bakhodirovich	
MULTIVARIATE ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING HOUSEHOLD INCOME IN SURXONDARYO REGION	93
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norquchqor qizi	
СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЦИФРОВЫХ УСЛУГ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА И УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	99
Юсифов Магамед Исмаил оглу, Гасанли Расул Шахин оглу, Белалова Гузаль Анваровна	
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY.....	105
Xudayberdiyeva Kamila Sadillovna, Fozilova Zumrad Ahmadovna	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF CLOTHING MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	111
Axmedova Gaziza Azim kizi	
КОМПЛЕКСНАЯ ОЦЕНКА ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕГИОНАЛЬНОГО АГРОПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО ИНТЕГРИРОВАНИЯ НА ОСНОВЕ МОДЕЛИ АНР-TOPIS	115
Аликулов А.Б.	
APPLICATION OF CLUSTER METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE AND IMPROVEMENT OF ECONOMIC MECHANISMS IN SAMARKAND CITY	121
Tashov Mizrob Maxmudovich	
THE ROLE AND PROSPECTS OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN THE SERVICE SECTOR.....	130
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF REGIONAL ENTERPRISES	135
Nigora Zokirjon qizi Toxirova	
CURRENT STATE OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE METHODOLOGY OF ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY INDICATORS	142
Temurbek Olimovich Mamayunusov	
PRESUPPOSITION SHIFTS IN CROSS-LINGUISTIC RENDERING OF ANECDOTAL NARRATIVES: A COMPARATIVE INQUIRY INTO TRIGGER RETENTION AND TRANSFORMATION	148
Umaraliyeva Dildora Taxirjanovna	

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND RURAL PUBLIC SERVICE QUALITY: AN EMPIRICAL ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS.....	156
<i>Bek Hunsia, Feruza Mansurovna Ollokulova</i>	
COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF WOMEN’S LABOR ACTIVITY ON THE EFFICIENCY OF THE ECONOMIC SYSTEM.....	164
<i>Ahrorova Asila Abduaziz qizi</i>	
IMPROVING TAX ADMINISTRATION IN THE ENTREPRENEURIAL ENVIRONMENT.....	170
<i>Azizbek Khurramov</i>	
FORMATION OF FINANCIAL RESULTS AT MOTOR TRANSPORT ENTERPRISES.....	180
<i>Shanazarova Nilufar Baratovna</i>	
ARIMA-BASED ANALYSIS OF SMALL BUSINESS ACTIVITY IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF SURKHANDARYA REGION.....	185
<i>Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi</i>	
ASSESSMENT OF AGRARIAN SECTOR EFFICIENCY THROUGH THE SFA MODEL.....	192
<i>Utanov Bunyod Kuvandikovich</i>	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫМ ВНЕШНИМ ДОЛГОМ.....	196
<i>Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович, Жуманазаров Шахобиддин Дилмурод угли</i>	
MODERN METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO MANAGING EDUCATIONAL SERVICES MARKETING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	201
<i>Shamshieva Nargizakhon Nosirkhuja kizi</i>	
FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT OF FOREIGN AND DOMESTIC COTTON GINNING ENTERPRISES: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, DIAGNOSTICS, AND IMPROVEMENT DIRECTIONS.....	208
<i>Orif Jumayevich Murodov</i>	
ANALYSIS OF THE INSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF STATE INTERVENTION IN THE PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT PROCESS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	219
<i>Atakulov Askad Raimkulovich</i>	

ANALYSIS OF THE INSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF STATE INTERVENTION IN THE PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT PROCESS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article analyzes the institutional foundations of state intervention in product quality management practices under the conditions of New Uzbekistan and examines their impact on economic efficiency. The study highlights the relationship between product quality and competitiveness, mechanisms for improving quality control, and the importance of modern quality management systems. Particular attention is given to state regulatory instruments, standardization, and certification processes as important factors in national economic development. The findings demonstrate that strengthening institutional approaches to product quality management contributes to higher production efficiency and increased consumer confidence.

Key words: management, quality, product quality, quality management, quality control, quality management system, standardization, certification, competitiveness, economic efficiency.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются институциональные основы государственного вмешательства в практику управления качеством продукции в условиях Нового Узбекистана и их влияние на экономическую эффективность. В исследовании раскрываются взаимосвязь между качеством продукции и конкурентоспособностью, механизмы совершенствования контроля качества, а также значение современных систем менеджмента качества. Особое внимание уделено инструментам государственного регулирования, процессам стандартизации и сертификации как важным факторам развития национальной экономики. Результаты исследования показывают, что усиление институциональных подходов к управлению качеством продукции способствует повышению эффективности производства и укреплению доверия потребителей.

Ключевые слова: управление, качество, качество продукции, управление качеством, контроль качества, система менеджмента качества, стандартизация, сертификация, конкурентоспособность, экономическая эффективность.

INTRODUCTION

Product quality is considered one of the key factors in ensuring the sustainable development of any country's economy. Improving the effectiveness of product quality management is essential for fully satisfying consumer needs, ensuring market competitiveness, and increasing export potential.

Today, quality management is widely applied in various sectors of national economies across different countries, including industry, services, agriculture, healthcare, education, and other fields. Numerous factors influence product quality, and their scientifically grounded analysis plays a decisive role in the successful implementation of quality management.

Under the conditions of New Uzbekistan, priority is being given to reforms aimed at integrating the quality of domestically produced goods and services into international standards. Through this process, it is intended to encourage local manufacturing entities to enter foreign markets, ensure a positive foreign trade balance, and increase the efficiency of utilizing the export potential of various sectors. In particular, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized that "the expected results in exporting products to European countries have not been achieved," which indicates the priority being placed on systemic reforms in this area. In this regard, it

is necessary to improve the efficiency of utilizing local opportunities through research into the scientific and theoretical foundations of product quality management

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

In the scientific research of foreign economists such as E.Q. Borazon, H.M. Liu, R.A. Saleh, and S. Sahoo, the improvement of product quality management efficiency has been identified as an integral component of corporate management strategies aimed at increasing competitiveness. Meanwhile, researchers such as D. Kafetzopoulos and H.S. Al-Dhaafri have proven that the effectiveness of product quality management is closely linked to the innovative activity of enterprises.

In general, increasing the opportunities for utilizing the export potential of the sectors of the national economy today requires the formation of a quality management system integrated with globally recognized standards such as “bio,” “organic,” and “eco” standards. This, in turn, creates the necessity for establishing an effective product quality management system adapted to local conditions through a systematic analysis of research conducted in economic science and the results achieved in the field of product quality management.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

During the research process, methods such as systematic analysis, historicity and logicity, induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, comparative and selective research, monographic analysis, and grouping methods were applied.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Within the framework of the sectors of the national economy, the system of standards established for product and service quality management changes depending on the sector-specific characteristics of the goods or services produced by enterprises, as well as on the requirements of general and specialized legislation. In particular, a national standards system for determining product quality has been developed in the country, and the functioning of this system is based on the following principles (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Principles of the Functioning of the National Standards System for State Regulation of Product Quality Management in Uzbekistan¹

- Principle of legality – implies that the quality of products manufactured by an enterprise, including the quality management system operating within the enterprise, must comply with the requirements established by current legislation.
- Principle of mutual agreement among stakeholders – means that the national standards system developed for a particular type of product should not contradict the interests of consumers, producers, or participants in the product manufacturing and supply chain, and should ensure consistency and proportionality among them. In other words, the standards developed for a product during the production process must correspond to the quality standards established for its raw materials.
- Principle of objectivity – предусматривает the application of an impartial approach in developing national quality standards for any type of product and in monitoring the compliance of manufactured products with established standard requirements.

¹ Source: Author's own elaboration.

- Principle of solidarity and cooperation – refers to the establishment of cooperative relations among responsible state authorities, manufacturing enterprises, and consumers in eliminating and preventing duplication and possible contradictions within the national product quality standards system.
- Principle of brand protection – means preventing situations and relationships that may undermine or damage the reputation of the product brand when developing the national standards system for determining product quality, regardless of the type of product, manufacturing enterprise, industry, region, country, or form of ownership of the producer.
- Principle of openness and transparency – implies ensuring transparency in the development of the national standards system, the assessment of whether produced goods and services comply with established standards, and the disclosure of information regarding the obtained results, as well as transparency in the socio-economic relations arising within this process.

The institutional foundations of state regulation of product quality management practices in the country are reflected in the activities of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Uzbekistan Technical Regulation Agency, authorized state administration bodies in the field of technical regulation, state and economic management bodies engaged in technical regulation activities, the national standardization body, the accreditation body, expert commissions in the field of technical regulation, conformity assessment bodies, and testing laboratories (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Institutional Foundations of State Regulation of Product Quality Management Practices in Uzbekistan²

At the same time, specialized research institutes in the field of quality and standardization, including higher educational institutions, business entities (associations established within production sectors such as the Food Industry Association, the Light Industry and Textile Association, the Farmers' Association, etc.), and consumer associations also participate in the state regulation of product quality management practices in the country. These institutions perform the following functions:

- Specialized research institutes in quality and standardization, including higher educational institutions – develop scientifically grounded proposals and recommendations on product quality management, improvement of the national product standards system, integration into international quality standards, enhancement of methodological approaches to quality assessment, and other related areas.
- Business entities and consumer associations – operate as institutional forms of public oversight over the quality of manufactured products.

In the state regulation of product quality management practices, government control is exercised through the activities of the Ministries of Internal Affairs and Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the Committees for Sanitary-Epidemiological Welfare and Public Health, Competition Development and Consumer Rights Protection, Taxation, and Veterinary and Livestock Development in cases involving the production or circulation of products that have not passed national quality certification, counterfeit goods, expired products, or products unfit for consumption in local consumer markets. Each organization performs the relevant functional duties presented in Table 1.

² Source: Author's own elaboration.

Through these measures, it becomes possible to “ensure the protection of consumer rights, prevent the production and circulation of uncertified, expired, counterfeit, and unfit consumer goods, and provide the population with quality consumer products (Table 1).

Table 1. Institutional Foundations of State Control over Product Quality in Local Markets and Their Functions³

No	Organization	Control Functions of the Organizations
1	Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan	Sale of low-quality or counterfeit medicines and medical products Sale of counterfeit, uncertified, and unregistered medicines and medical products Sale of prescription medicines and medical products without a prescription
2	Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan	Production or sale of products using the name or trademark of a manufacturer (or an imitation thereof), or the indication of the place of origin of goods Violation of copyright and related rights Violation of rights to an invention, utility model, and industrial design
3	Committee for Sanitary-Epidemiological Welfare and Public Health	Production or sale of products using the name or trademark of a manufacturer (or an imitation thereof), or the indication of the place of origin of goods Violation of copyright and related rights Violation of rights to an invention, utility model, and industrial design
4	Tax Committee	Sale of alcoholic beverages and tobacco products with counterfeit excise stamps or without excise stamps Sale of alcoholic beverages and tobacco products without mandatory digital labeling codes Sale of alcoholic beverages and tobacco products without authorization Sale of low-quality alcohol and alcoholic products
5	Committee for Competition Development and Consumer Rights Protection	Failure of a retail outlet to display price tags on goods offered for sale Difference between the displayed price of goods and the price indicated on the cash receipt Sale of expired products Sale of medicines and medical products with markups exceeding the established price limits Sale of goods that are required to indicate the production date and expiration date without complying with such requirements
6	Committee for Veterinary and Livestock Development	Production or sale of meat, meat products, milk, and dairy products unfit for consumption Sale of meat, meat products, milk, and dairy products without veterinary inspection Sale of meat, meat products, milk, and dairy products in unauthorized locations Transportation of meat and meat products using unauthorized vehicles

Through the establishment of a state-controlled system for monitoring product quality in local markets, achievements have been made in “ensuring the protection of consumer rights, strengthening public oversight over the production and circulation of uncertified, expired, counterfeit, and unfit goods, and restricting such practices.” At the same time, in recent years, priority has been given to large-scale reforms aimed at the country’s accession to the World Trade Organization, which has increased the need to develop systematic measures for integrating the national product quality standards system into global standards.

As a result, in accordance with global requirements for product quality, a “special certification and mandatory state registration procedure for high-risk product groups” has been developed. This has contributed to the effective organization of state regulation in the fields of standardization, certification, and metrology, the introduction of digital technologies to make the system transparent, efficient, and corruption-free, as well as the acceleration of harmonization processes with World Trade Organization standards.

Furthermore, starting from 2025, the country has introduced a unified voluntary environmental labeling system for products and services called the “Yashil Belgi” (Green Label), in accordance with the ISO 14024 international standard for Type I life-cycle-based ecolabeling. Within this framework, the Ministry of Ecology of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been assigned responsibilities to develop and continuously improve environmental standards for different types of products and services, as well as to participate in the product eco-labeling process.

³ Annex 2 to the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-110 “On Additional Measures Aimed at Ensuring the Population with High-Quality Consumer Goods”, dated 04.04.2023.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the conducted analysis, it has been identified that the state regulation of product quality management in the country is consistently developing through regulatory-legal, institutional, quality promotion culture, and practical implementation dimensions. In our view, taking into account the ongoing reforms and positive developments in state regulation of product quality management practices, it is appropriate to further strengthen the implementation of the following measures in the coming years:

Deepening institutional reforms – establishing coordination councils among authorized bodies involved in the state regulation of product quality management practices, as well as expanding the organization of quality control laboratories and centers at the regional level.

Improving human resource provision – developing educational programs in higher education institutions aimed at training specialists in quality management and further enhancing their professional qualifications.

Technical and financial support – creating a system of subsidies and grants for manufacturing enterprises that have implemented or are in the process of implementing global quality standards, including the wider introduction of digitalized systems for product quality control in local markets.

Formation of a quality culture among the population and business entities – this includes increasing public awareness on consumer rights, as well as strengthening a unified and consistent understanding of product quality between consumers and producers through effective information dissemination mechanisms.

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